

THE ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF COLLOIDAL SILICIC ACID. PART II. INTERACTION WITH NEUTRAL SALTS.*

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The capacities of different cations to liberate acid from colloidal silicic acid are in the order $Ba^{++} > Ca^{++} > Na^+ > Li^+$, i.e., in agreement with the lyotrope series. The total amount of acid liberated by $BaCl_2$, $Ba(CH_3COO)_2$, $CaCl_2$ and $Ca(CH_3COO)_2$ is considerably greater than that neutralised at the first inflexion point in the titration curve of silicic acid sol with a dilute base. At low concentrations, alkali metal cations only effect an osmotic displacement of the mobile H^+ ions. The results have been discussed in the light of the theory of electrical double layer and secondary adsorption of ions.

The nature of the interaction between neutral salts and colloidal silicic acid has been the subject of controversies. Joseph and Hancock (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 202) regarded the reaction as an ordinary double decomposition process in which insoluble silicates are formed with the liberation of acids, the equilibrium condition being determined by the solubility of the solid salts (silicates formed by the interaction) and of silicic acid. Mukherjee and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1926, 3023), on the other hand, considered that the reaction is not a simple chemical process but consists of interchanges between the hydrogen ions present in the double layers associated with the colloidal particles (Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103; *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 321) of the sol and the cations of the added salts. According to them the amount of hydrogen ions exchanged at equilibrium is, therefore, determined by the relative adsorbabilities of the cations of the salts rather than by the solubilities of the corresponding solid salts. It follows from the theory of electrical adsorption of oppositely charged ions by charged colloidal surface postulated by Mukherjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103; *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 321; *Kolloid Z.*, 1939, 62, 257) that the energy of electrical adsorption of barium ions is greater than that of calcium ions. Barium chloride should, therefore, on interaction with the sol, liberate more acid than calcium chloride. Solubility considerations, however, lead one to expect a greater relative effect of calcium chloride because of the greater insolubility of calcium silicate. These conflicting inferences from the rival theories can be put to experimental test. Mukherjee and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) observed that the supernatant liquid of purified silica gel showed

* The results given in this paper have been taken from the annual reports (1936-37, 1937-38, 1938-39) submitted to the Imperial Council of Agricultural Research, India.

a greater concentration of H^+ -ions on the addition of barium chloride than calcium chloride; an observation which supports their theory. They, however, measured the H^+ -ion concentration by the indicator method. The limitations of this method for measurements with unbuffered acid system are well known. It is also necessary to have more complete evidence which should preferably be confirmed by different methods.

In this paper a careful study has been made by comparing (1) the variations in the H^+ -ion concentration of silicic acid sols on the progressive additions of solutions of neutral salts and (2) the total amount of acid liberated on continually leaching the sols with these solutions till the leachates show a neutral reaction. The hydrogen electrode and in some cases the glass electrode have been used for the measurements. Other salts have also been used. The experimental arrangements were the same as those described in Part I (p. 583).

Variation in the p_H values of Silicic Acid Sols on the Addition of Neutral Salt Solutions.

From the titration curves given in Figures 1, 2 and 3 and the results given in Table I it will be seen that (i) potassium chloride has a smaller effect on the lowering of p_H of the sols than barium chloride or calcium chloride and (ii) the p_H decreases rapidly in the initial stages of the titrations but the rate of decrease diminishes with the gradual additions of the salt solutions.

TABLE I.

Sol.	Salt conc.	Lowering of the p_H with $BaCl_2$.	Lowering of the p_H with $CaCl_2$.	Sol.	Salt conc.	Lowering of the p_H with $BaCl_2$.	Lowering of the p_H with $CaCl_2$.
L'	0			N	0		
	$2.0 \times 10^3 N$	0.20	0.14		$2.0 \times 10^3 N$	0.19	0.07
	4.0	0.23	0.14		5.0	0.24	0.13
	7.0	0.23	0.13		10.0	0.26	0.13
	13.0	0.21	0.12		20.0	0.26	0.13
	20.0	0.20	0.13		40.0	0.25	0.12
	32.5	0.22	0.13	55.0	0.28	0.12	
M	0			P	0		
	2.0	0.24	0.17		2.0	0.27	0.14
	5.0	0.23	0.20		3.0	0.30	0.18
	10.0	0.26	0.22		5.0	0.32	0.21
	20.0	0.29	0.25		10.0	0.31	0.22
	40.0	0.34	0.25		20.0	0.31	0.23
	80.0	0.39	0.28	40.0	0.32	0.22	
				80.0	0.34	0.22	

The changes in the p_H may be ascribed at least in part, to changes in the liquid junction potential and in the H^+ -ion activities and therefore require to be corrected. Control measurements were therefore carried out with hydrochloric acid having nearly the same p_H as the sol. The lowering of p_H observed with the sols has been corrected for that observed with HCl in the actual measurements and the corrected data are given in Table I.

A definitely greater lowering of p_H on addition of barium chloride than calcium chloride is evident. The greater effect of barium is in agreement

FIG. 1.

Sol K.

with the theory of electrical adsorption. Calcium hydroxide, however, reacts more strongly with silicic acid sol than baryta. (*vide Part I, This Journal*, p. 583).

Curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 1 obtained with sol K are interesting as they bring out a factor which sometimes obscures the comparison. It will be seen that barium chloride lowers the p_H to a greater extent in the initial stages but at concentrations higher than 0.0085N-calcium chloride shows a greater effect. But sol K was found to have set to a gel in presence of 0.0085N-barium chloride but not of calcium chloride. The setting renders difficult an intimate mixing of the electrolyte with the sol.

FIG. 2.

Sol L'.

5-Sol-CaCl₂; 6 Sol-BaCl₂; 5'-HCl-CaCl₂; 6'-HCl-BaCl₂.

Estimation of the Total Amount of Acid liberated by continually Leaching the Sol with Solutions of BaCl₂ and CaCl₂.

In comparing the relative effects of barium and calcium chloride an estimation of the total acidity of the sols in the presence of these salts would be more helpful and decisive. The sols, however, set on trying to titrate them with bases in the presence of barium or calcium chloride. The amount

TABLE II.

Sol.	Amount of acid liberated in normality			
	BaCl ₂ .	CaCl ₂ .	NaCl.	*LiCl.
M 1st leachate	16.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	11.4 × 10 ⁻⁵		
2nd	5.8	5.4		
3rd	3.6	3.4		
4th	Nil	Nil		
Total	25.4	20.2		
Q 1st leachate	17.0	15.0	11.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	9.8 × 10 ⁻⁵
2nd	8.4	4.0	4.0	4.6
3rd	3.8	2.6	3.0	1.0
4th	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Total	29.2	21.6	18.8	15.4

* 0.013N solution of LiCl has been used for leaching sol Q.

of acid liberated from the sol by continually leaching it with barium or calcium chloride has, therefore, been estimated. The total amounts of acid liberated by NaCl and LiCl from sol Q have also been estimated and incorporated in Table II for comparison. Normal solutions of neutral salts have been used for sol M and centinormal solutions of neutral salts for sol Q.

The amount of acid liberated by the salts are considerably greater, specially by BaCl₂ and CaCl₂ than that neutralised at the first inflexion point in the titration curve of sols with dilute bases ($9.0 \times 10^{-3}N$ and $14.5 \times 10^{-3}N$ for sols M and Q respectively). It will be seen that BaCl₂ and CaCl₂, on account of their greater electrical adsorption, have displaced greater amount of acid than that liberated by NaCl or LiCl. The capacities of the different cations to liberate acid are in the order Ba⁺⁺ > Ca⁺⁺ > Na⁺ > Li⁺. The results also confirm beyond doubt the greater relative effect of barium than calcium ions.

The reaction between the sol and the salts (here, chlorides) is really a balanced one and can be represented as follows :

where H stand for the 'mobile' as well as the 'bound' H⁺-ions present in the double layer and X represents the colloidal anion. With the progress of the reaction there will be an increase in the concentration of hydrochloric acid, which being highly dissociated, the H⁺-ion concentration will greatly increase and consequently the backward reaction will be favoured more and more. The displacement of H⁺-ions from the double layer by the cations of the added salt will be rendered more and more difficult. In view of the weaker dissociation of acetic acid it was thought that the displacement of the H⁺-ions would be more complete if acetates instead of chlorides were used. The results obtained with sol Q are given in Table III. Centinormal solutions of neutral salts have been used.

TABLE III.

	Total acid (CH ₃ COO) ₂ Ba.	(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Ca.
1st leachate	$32.5 \times 10^{-5}N$	$38.0 \times 10^{-5}N$
2nd	22.5	5.0
3rd	11.5	Nil
4th	3.5	—
Total	70.0	43.0

As expected the amount of acid liberated by barium and calcium acetates is considerably greater than that liberated by the corresponding chlorides. Barium acetate again liberates more acid than calcium acetate,

The results show that the amount of acid liberated is highest in the case of $\text{Ba}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$. Even then, the total amount of acid liberated by $\text{Ba}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ is only 4.5 milliequivalents per 100 g. of colloid. This value is extremely low in comparison with that observed in the case of most hydrogen clays or bentonites.

According to Mukherjee's theory, the solid surface of the colloidal particles of silicic acid carries anions constituting the fixed layer of primarily adsorbed anions, some kind of silicate ions. An equivalent amount of hydrogen ions held on or near the surface satisfies the condition of electroneutrality of the system. A part of these hydrogen ions remains fixed on the surface by electrostatic or chemical forces and these constitute what he terms the secondarily adsorbed layer, while the rest of the hydrogen ions forms the mobile sheet of the double layer. These mobile hydrogen ions register their activities on a hydrogen electrode and give rise to the observed p_n of the sol (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*).

The first process, *viz.*, the displacement of the mobile hydrogen ions, is the result of osmotic diffusion and should not materially alter the hydrogen ion activity of the sol as the total number of osmotically active hydrogen ions in the system does not change. The second process, namely, the displacement of bound or secondarily adsorbed hydrogen ions should increase the hydrogen ion activity of the systems. The displacement of bound hydrogen ions depends on the adsorbabilities of the cations and is determined by their valencies and mobilities, when the potential energy of resulting ion pairs is purely the result of electrostatic attractive forces between the primarily adsorbed ion and the hydrated cation constituting them.

In the following section the existence or otherwise of the first process has been examined. The existence of the second process follows from the data in Tables I, II and III.

Displacement of Mobile Hydrogen Ions by the Cation of the Added Salt.

The weak electrical adsorption of alkali metal ions renders it possible that in low concentrations they would not be capable of displacing to any large extent the bound hydrogen ions and would produce only an osmotic displacement of mobile hydrogen ions from the double layer to the bulk phase. Consequently there will be no appreciable change in the p_n of the sol,

The p_H variation on addition of KCl at low concentrations to the sol K are given below.

TABLE IV.

	p_H			*Total acidity.
	Hydrogen electrode.	Glass electrode.	Average.	
Sol K	4.00	3.97	3.98	$10.00 \times 10^{-5}N$
	3.92	4.02		
	3.98	4.00		
Ultrafiltrate of sol K	—	5.09		1.2
Sol K + 0.01N-KCl	3.80	3.87	3.86	
	3.91	3.87		
Ultrafiltrate of above mixture	4.10	4.16	4.13	11.4

FIG. 3.

Conc. of added salt $\times 10^3 N$.
 7-Sol-CaCl₂ ; 8-Sol-BaCl₂;
 7'-HCl-CaCl₂ ; 8'-HCl-BaCl₂.

The above results show that (i) the total acidity of the ultrafiltrate of the sol + salt mixture is practically equal to that of the sol, though the total acidity of the ultrafiltrate of the sol itself is only about 10% of that of the sol; (ii) the addition of 0.01N-KCl produces a change in the p_H of the sol from 3.98 to 3.86 owing mainly to the changes in the liquid junction potential referred to earlier (*vide* curves 3 and 4); (iii) the addition of KCl,

however, has brought down the p_H of the ultrafiltrate from 5.09 to 4.13, the latter p_H is almost equal to that of the sol and the sol + salt mixture, showing that the mobile hydrogen ions, which could not originally pass through the ultrafilter membrane, can do so on the addition of KCl at the

* Total acidity values have been calculated from the inflexion points in the titration curves with dilute bases.

TABLE V.

	p_H			Free acidity.	Total acidity.
	Hydrogen electrode.	Quinhydrone electrode.	Average.		
Sol Q	4'09	4'12	4'11	$7.8 \times 10^{-6}N$	$14.5 \times 10^{-6}N$
	4'10				
	4'10				
Ultrafiltrate of above	5'02	5'07	5'05	0'89	1'2
Sol Q 0'01N-LiCl	4'12	4'10	4'11	7'8	*
	4'12				
Ultrafiltrate of the above	4'14	4'08	4'11	7'8	7.4
	4'08				8.0
	4'07				8.2
	4'10				
			Average	7.9	

above concentrations. Similar results with lithium chloride using sol Q are shown in Table V.

As in the previous case, the free acidities of the sol, the sol + salt mixture and of the ultrafiltrate of the mixture are in mutual agreement indicating a complete displacement of the mobile hydrogen ions by the lithium ions. The total acid of the ultrafiltrate is also in fair agreement with its free acid. This is to be expected as the ultrafiltrate should contain only hydrochloric acid. The total acid of the sol, on the other hand, is considerably higher than its free acid showing that the inflexion point in the titration curve from which this total acidity has been calculated involves the neutralisation of some bound H^+ -ions in addition to the mobile hydrogen ions initially present in the sol.

It is intended to study in further detail the interaction between colloidal silicic acid and cations of the alkali and alkaline earth metals.

C O N C L U S I O N .

The p_H of a silicic acid sol is considerably lowered on the addition of neutral salts. The effect of alkali metal cations is much smaller than that

* Could not be determined as the mixture set on the addition of alkali.

of the alkaline earth ones. The Ba^{++} -ions are more effective than the Ca^{++} -ions.

The total amount of acid liberated by continually leaching a silicic acid sol with neutral solutions of $BaCl_2$, $CaCl_2$, $Ba(CH_3COO)_2$ and $Ca(CH_3COO)_2$ is considerably greater than that neutralised at the first inflexion point in the titration curve of the sol with a dilute base. Ba- and Ca-acetates liberate more acid than the corresponding chlorides. The total amount of acid liberated by Ba-salts is much greater than that liberated by Ca-salts. The capacities of different cations to liberate acid from silicic acid sol are in the order : $Ba^{++} > Ca^{++} > Na^+ > Li^+$.

At low concentrations the alkali metal cations on account of their weak electrical adsorption can not easily displace the 'bound' H^+ -ions but only effect an osmotic displacement of the 'mobile' hydrogen ions.

The results have been discussed in the light of the theory of electrical double layer and of the secondary adsorption of ions.

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